

Deep Learning for image analysis

Ali Ben Abbes
FRB-CESAB
ali.benabbes@fondationbiodiversite.fr

Jeaneth Machicao
Universidade de São Paulo
machicao@usp.br

PARSEC is a project sponsored by the Belmont Forum as part of its Collaborative Research Action (CRA) on Science-Driven e-Infrastructures Innovation (SEI), with funding from FAPESP, the ANR, JST and the NSF, with collaborators from Australia, and support from the synthesis centre CESAB of the French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity.

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

01
General context

02
Deep Learning pipeline

03
Hands-on

- Area of study
- Socioeconomic indicators
- Satellite imagery

DL methods can provide valuable information for environmental and socioeconomic monitoring, facilitating initiatives aimed at sustainable development and biodiversity conservation in the national territory!

State-of-the-art: Deep Learning methods based on remote sensing images for poverty estimation

[Ayush et al., 2016]

Proceedings of the Twenty-Ninth International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI-20)
Special Track on AI for Computational Sustainability and Human Well-being

Generating Interpretable Poverty Maps using Object Detection in Satellite Images

Kumar Ayush^{1*}, Burak Uz Kent^{1*}, Marshall Burke²,
David Lobell² and Stefano Ermon¹

[Jean et al., 2016]

Science

Combining satellite imagery and machine learning to predict poverty

Neal Jean,^{1,2*} Marshall Burke,^{3,4,5*} Michael Xie,¹ W. Matthew Davis,⁴
David B. Lobell,^{3,4} Stefano Ermon¹

2016 • VOL 353 ISSUE 6301

[Suel et al., 2019]

scientific reports

Measuring social, environmental and health inequalities using deep learning and street imagery

Esra Suel , John W. Polak, James E. Bennett & Majid Ezzati

Scientific Reports **9**, Article number: 6229 (2019)

[Yeh et al., 2020]

Using publicly available satellite imagery and deep learning to understand economic well-being in Africa

Christopher Yeh ^{1,2,7}, Anne Driscoll³, George Azzari^{2,4}, Zhongyi Tang⁵,
Stefano Ermon

Case study: Yeh et al., (2020)

Article | [Open Access](#) | Published: 22 May 2020

Using publicly available satellite imagery and deep learning to understand economic well-being in Africa

Christopher Yeh, Anthony Perez, Anne Driscoll, George Azzari, Zhongyi Tang, David Lobell, Stefano Ermon & Marshall Burke [✉](#)

Nature Communications 11, Article number: 2583 (2020) | [Cite this article](#)

13k Accesses | 5 Citations | 121 Altmetric | [Metrics](#)

Reporting summary

Further information on research design is available in the [Nature Research Reporting Summary](#) linked to this article.

Data availability

Data to replicate all findings in the paper are available at https://github.com/sustainlab-group/africa_poverty.

Code availability

Code to replicate all findings in the paper are available at https://github.com/sustainlab-group/africa_poverty.

Source github

GitHub link: https://github.com/sustainlab-group/africa_poverty

Contributors 3

- **chrisyeh96** Christopher Yeh
- **amd112** Anne Driscoll
- **AnthonyPerez** Anthony Perez

sustainlab-group / africa_poverty

amd112 Update README.md 3s820ff on 17 Aug 2020 83 commits

batchers	Update get_lsms_tfreord_pairs() in delta_batcher.py to return values...	2 years ago
code_figs	update fig1	7 months ago
data	Merge lsms_labels_index_agg_households.csv into lsms_labels_index_...	9 months ago
data_analysis	Merge lsms_labels_index_agg_households.csv into lsms_labels_index_...	9 months ago
download	small updates	10 months ago
model_analysis	add lsmsdelta_resnet.ipynb	13 months ago
models	Update notebooks	13 months ago
preprocessing	LSMS index-of-delta max activating maps	13 months ago
processed_fig	final fixes to survey data for Fig 1	10 months ago
raw_fig	final fixes to survey data for Fig 1	10 months ago
scripts	DHS incountry training	2 years ago
utils	LSMS index-of-delta max activating maps	13 months ago
.flake8	environment setup	2 years ago
.gitignore	Cleanup	11 months ago
README.md	Update README.md	7 months ago
env.yml	Update env.yml with specific versions	10 months ago
extract_features_dhs.py	Cleanup	2 years ago
mypy.ini	Add mypy.ini. Update gitignore	2 years ago
train_delta.py	Print start and end time in train_directly.py and train_delta.py	2 years ago
train_delta_lsms_runner.py	Add keep_frac procedure to train_directly_runner.py	2 years ago
train_directly.py	Fix bugs in train_directly.py	2 years ago
train_directly_runner.py	Cleanup	2 years ago

TABLE OF CONTENTS

01

General context

02

Deep Learning pipeline

03

Hands-on

- Area of study
- Socioeconomic indicators
- Satellite imagery

Deep Learning pipeline

Deep Learning pipeline

6 steps for Deep Learning pipeline

Download satellite images from GEE

Process satellite images

Prepare data files

Run a baseline ML method

Train Convolutional Neural Network models

Extract learned feature representations

Hardware and Software requirements

This code was tested on a system with the following specifications:

- operating system: Ubuntu 16.04.6 LTS
- CPU: Intel Xeon Silver 4110
- memory (RAM): 125GB
- disk storage: 500GB
- GPU: 1x NVIDIA Titan Xp

The main software requirements are Python 3.7 with TensorFlow r1.15, and R 3.6. The complete list of required packages and library are listed in the `env.yml` file, which is meant to be used with `conda` (version 4.8.3). See [here](#) for instructions on installing conda via Miniconda. Once conda is installed, run the following command to set up the conda environment:

```
conda env create -f env.yml
```

Hardware and Software requirements

This code was tested on a system with the following specifications:

- operating system: Ubuntu 16.04.6 LTS
- CPU: Intel Xeon Silver 4110
- memory (RAM): 125GB
- disk storage: 500GB
- GPU: 1x NVIDIA Titan Xp

The main software requirements are Python 3.7 with TensorFlow r1.15, and R 3.6. The complete list of required packages and library are listed in the `env.yml` file, which is meant to be used with `conda` (version 4.8.3). See [here](#) for instructions on installing conda via Miniconda. Once conda is installed, run the following command to set up the conda environment:

```
conda env create -f env.yml
```

22 lines (22 sloc) | 501 Bytes

```
1 name: py37
2 channels:
3   - conda-forge
4   - defaults
5 dependencies:
6   - python=3.7.7
7   - cartopy=0.18.0
8   - earthengine-api=0.1.221
9   - flake8=3.8.1
10  - jupyterlab=2.1.2
11  - jupyter_contrib_nbextensions=0.5.1
12  - matplotlib=3.2.1
13  - mypy=0.770
14  - nb_conda=2.2.1 # optional, useful for running R in Jupyter notebooks
15  - numpy=1.18.4
16  - pandas=1.0.3
17  - pillow=7.1.2
18  - scikit-learn=0.23.0
19  - scipy=1.4.1
20  - seaborn=0.10.1
21  - tqdm=4.46.0
22  - tensorflow-gpu=1.15.0 # only supports up to Python 3.7
```

Hardware and Software requirements

This code was tested on a system with the following specifications:

- operating system: Ubuntu 16.04.6 LTS
- CPU: Intel Xeon Silver 4110
- memory (RAM): 125GB
- disk storage: 500GB
- GPU: 1x NVIDIA Titan Xp

The main software requirements are Python 3.7 with TensorFlow r1.15, and R 3.6. The complete list of required packages and library are listed in the `env.yml` file, which is meant to be used with `conda` (version 4.8.3). See [here](#) for instructions on installing conda via Miniconda. Once conda is installed, run the following command to set up the conda environment:

```
conda env create -f env.yml
```

If you are using a GPU, you may need to also install CUDA 10 and cuDNN 7.

22 lines (22 sloc) | 501 Bytes

```
1 name: py37
2 channels:
3   - conda-forge
4   - defaults
5 dependencies:
6   - python=3.7.7
7   - cartopy=0.18.0
8   - earthengine-api=0.1.221
9   - flake8=3.8.1
10  - jupyterlab=2.1.2
11  - jupyter_contrib_nbextensions=0.5.1
12  - matplotlib=3.2.1
13  - mypy=0.770
14  - nb_conda=2.2.1 # optional, useful for running R in Jupyter notebooks
15  - numpy=1.18.4
16  - pandas=1.0.3
17  - pillow=7.1.2
18  - scikit-learn=0.23.0
19  - scipy=1.4.1
20  - seaborn=0.10.1
21  - tqdm=4.46.0
22  - tensorflow-gpu=1.15.0 # only supports up to Python 3.7
```

1. Download satellite images from GEE

Storage

Images are saved in gzipped TF-Record format.

```
data/
  dhs_tfrecords_raw/
    angola_2011_00.tfrecord.gz
    ...
    zimbabwe_2015_00.tfrecord.gz
  lsms_tfrecords_raw/
    ethiopia_2011_00.tfrecord.gz
    ...
    uganda_2013_00.tfrecord.gz
```

	Storage	Expected Export Time
DHS	~16.0 GB	~24h
LSMS	~2.5 GB	~10h

Wealth index

	lat	lon	wealthpooled	country	year	urban	nl_mean	nl_center	households
0	-11.915085	22.876839	-1.019361	angola	2011	False	-0.086633	0.016189	37
1	-11.886975	22.924997	-1.090052	angola	2011	False	-0.097684	-0.173862	37
...
19667	-17.989489	31.033354	1.882921	zimbabwe	2015	True	0.515834	1.890566	26
19668	-17.998350	31.042618	1.880099	zimbabwe	2015	True	0.844067	1.456959	24

19669 rows x 9 columns

DHS villages

1. Download satellite images from GEE

Storage

Images are saved in gzipped TF-Record format.

```
data/
  dhs_tfrecords_raw/
    angola_2011_00.tfrecord.gz
    ...
    zimbabwe_2015_00.tfrecord.gz
  lsms_tfrecords_raw/
    ethiopia_2011_00.tfrecord.gz
    ...
    uganda_2013_00.tfrecord.gz
```

	Storage	Expected Export Time
DHS	~16.0 GB	~24h
LSMS	~2.5 GB	~10h

```
CHUNK_SIZE = None # set to a small number (<= 50) if Google Earth Engine reports memory errors
```

Chunk_size defines the number of satellite images in a record.

Wealth index

	lat	lon	wealthpoled	country	year	urban	nl_mean	nl_center	households
0	-11.915085	22.876839	-1.019361	angola	2011	False	-0.086633	0.016189	37
1	-11.886975	22.924997	-1.090052	angola	2011	False	-0.097684	-0.173862	37
...
19667	-17.989489	31.033354	1.882921	zimbabwe	2015	True	0.515834	1.890566	26
19668	-17.998350	31.042618	1.880099	zimbabwe	2015	True	0.844067	1.456959	24

19669 rows x 9 columns

DHS villages

2. Process satellite images

Storage

The format saved in the first step

```
data/
  dhs_tfrecoreds_raw/
    angola_2011_00.tfrecored.gz
    ...
    zimbabwe_2015_00.tfrecored.gz
  lsms_tfrecoreds_raw/
    ethiopia_2011_00.tfrecored.gz
    ...
    uganda_2013_00.tfrecored.gz
```

The format in the second step

```
lx_median_{year_range}_{country}_dhslocs_ee_export.tfrecored.gz'
```

A gap between the two steps

- Step 1: according to a single country, single year, and a chunk number. **{{country}}_{{year}}.tfrecored.gz**
- Step 2: combined for a single country
“lx_median_{year_range}_{country}_dhslocs_ee_export.tfrecored.gz”

2. Process satellite images

Storage

- Verifies that the TF-Records match the original CSV files.
- Splits each monolithic TF-Record file into one file per record.

Example of the Landsat and Nightlight images

2. Process satellite images

Storage

- Verifies that the TF-Records match the original CSV files.
- Splits each monolithic TF-Record file into one file per record.

Example of the Landsat and Nightlight images

3. Prepare data files

Storage

DHS Out-Of-Country folds

- Assign the clusters into **training** (train), **validation** (val), and **test** (test) splits.
- **Out-Of-Country**: assign entire countries to a split
- **In-Country**: different clusters within the same country to be assigned to different splits

DHS In-Country folds

4. Run a baseline ML method

Storage

DHS out-of-country folds

	r2	R2	mse	rank
KNN NL mean scalar	0.656155	0.655995	0.224643	0.747841
Ridge NL hist	0.649837	0.649817	0.228678	0.721912
Ridge RGB+NL hist	0.645250	0.645235	0.231670	0.743104
Ridge MS+NL hist	0.624247	0.623979	0.245551	0.723235
Ridge MS hist	0.277112	0.266370	0.479078	0.441796
Ridge NL center scalar	0.174327	0.150307	0.554870	0.512258
Ridge NL mean scalar	0.154494	0.130555	0.567769	0.493352
Ridge RGB hist	0.137615	0.134210	0.565382	0.344835

	lat	lon	country	year	urban	label	KNN NL mean scalar	Ridge MS hist	Ridge MS+NL hist	Ridge NL center scalar	Ridge NL hist	Ridge NL mean scalar	Ridge RGB hist	Ridge RGB+NL hist
0	-11.915085	22.876839	angola	2011	False	-1.019361	0.009687	-0.211548	-0.136666	-0.228462	-0.055156	-0.263023	-0.251392	-0.186917
1	-11.886975	22.924997	angola	2011	False	-1.090052	-0.133958	-0.331312	-0.216101	-0.308140	-0.125419	-0.268219	-0.218040	-0.272411
2	-9.498591	17.830034	angola	2011	False	-1.143002	-0.203931	-0.165150	-0.477106	-0.308140	-0.359495	-0.288863	-0.152893	-0.314883
3	-8.864000	13.240764	angola	2011	True	1.056769	1.476273	1.670230	1.087703	5.994556	1.583656	6.938411	0.773036	1.159504
...
19665	-18.031948	31.095280	zimbabwe	2015	True	1.268232	1.133497	0.674059	1.049920	0.197972	1.138939	0.250697	0.273901	1.130512
19666	-18.021593	31.084930	zimbabwe	2015	True	1.506693	1.195909	0.843300	1.145234	0.475418	1.225315	0.315318	0.306029	1.200058
19667	-17.989489	31.033354	zimbabwe	2015	True	1.882921	1.117101	0.847852	1.154399	0.413100	1.171655	0.165820	0.343904	1.216366
19668	-17.998350	31.042618	zimbabwe	2015	True	1.880099	1.127561	0.856749	1.166607	0.324282	1.188742	0.239271	0.333028	1.223257

DHS in-country folds

	r2	R2	mse	rank
KNN NL mean scalar	0.665153	0.664942	0.218801	0.758589
Ridge RGB+NL hist	0.661750	0.661657	0.220946	0.769465
Ridge MS+NL hist	0.658617	0.658598	0.222944	0.772393
GBT NL mean scalar	0.654257	0.654073	0.225899	0.744660
Ridge NL hist	0.652962	0.652907	0.226660	0.756101
Ridge MS hist	0.360743	0.360465	0.417632	0.542192
Ridge NL mean scalar	0.211494	0.195137	0.525595	0.618467
Ridge RGB hist	0.189704	0.189306	0.529403	0.416650

5. Train Convolutional Neural Network models

Storage

Settings for different CNN models:

Setting	CNN MS	CNN NL
ls_bands	ms	None
n1_band	None	split
imagenet_weights_path	./models/imagenet_resnet18_tensorpack.npz	None
hs_weight_init	samescaled	None

Settings for "out-of-country" vs. "in-country" experiments:

Setting	"out-of-country"	"in-country"
max_epochs	200	150
ooc	True	False
out_dir	./outputs/dhs_ooc/	./outputs/dhs_incountry/

5. Train Convolutional Neural Network models

Storage

```
python train_dhs.py \
  --label_name wealthpooled --batcher base \
  --model_name resnet --num_layers 18 \
  --lr_decay 0.96 --batch_size 64 \
  --gpu 0 --num_threads 5 \
  --cache train,train_eval,val \
  --augment True --eval_every 1 --print_every 40 \
  --ooc True --max_epochs 200 \
  --out_dir ./outputs/dhs_ooc/ \
  --keep_frac 0.25 --seed 456 \
  --experiment_name DHS_OOC_D_ms_samescaled_keep0.25_seed456 \
  --dataset DHS_OOC_D \
  --ls_bands ms --nl_band None \
  --lr 1e-2 --fc_reg 1e-3 --conv_reg 1e-3 \
  --imagenet_weights_path ./models/imagenet_resnet18_tensorpack.npz \
  --hs_weight_init samescaled
```

Settings for different CNN models:

Setting	CNN MS	CNN NL
ls_bands	ms	None
nl_band	None	split
imagenet_weights_path	./models/imagenet_resnet18_tensorpack.npz	None
hs_weight_init	samescaled	None

Settings for "out-of-country" vs. "in-country" experiments:

Setting	"out-of-country"	"in-country"
max_epochs	200	150
ooc	True	False
out_dir	./outputs/dhs_ooc/	./outputs/dhs_incountry/

6. Extract learned feature representations

- Extract learned feature representations.

Training script

```
--experiment_name DHS_00C_D_ms_samescaled_keep0.25_seed456 \
```

Extract features script

```
def get_full_experiment_name(experiment_name: str, batch_size: int,
                             fc_reg: float, conv_reg: float, lr: float,
                             tag: Optional[str] = None) -> str:
    """Returns a str
       '{experiment_name}_b{batch_size}_fc{fc_str}_conv{conv_str}_lr{lr_str}'
       where fc_str and conv_str are the numbers past the decimal for the fc/conv
       regularization parameters, and similarly for the learning rate lr.
       Optionally appends a tag to the end.
    """
    fc_str = param_to_str(fc_reg)
    conv_str = param_to_str(conv_reg)
    lr_str = param_to_str(lr)
    full_experiment_name = (
        f'{experiment_name}_b{batch_size}_fc{fc_str}_conv{conv_str}_lr{lr_str}'
```

TABLE OF CONTENTS

01

General context

02

Deep Learning pipeline

03

Hands-on

- Area of study
- Socioeconomic indicators
- Satellite imagery

HANDS-on (LABORATORY)

Area of study

- Vale do Ribeira

Socioeconomic indicator dataset

- Income

Satellite imagery

- Diurn

Vale do Ribeira

Vale do Ribeira

- 28,306 km² spread across São Paulo and Paraná
- 30 municipalities
- 954 census tracts
 - 880 are valid census tracts due to data privacy issues.
- Largest contiguous area of protected **Atlantic Forest** in Brazil, declared a Natural Heritage in 1999, which represents 21% of the remaining forest in the country.

Socioeconomic indicator dataset

Human Development Index (HDI)

Measures the various levels of social and economic development of countries

3 dimensions (Health, Education, and Economic Development)

- Income
- Longevity
- Literacy

Observed socioeconomic indicators in Vale do Ribeira

Longevity

Literacy

Income

1.0

0.8

0.6

0.4

0.2

0.0

All source code is

https://github.com/PARSECworld/WDS6_hands_on

```
git clone https://github.com/PARSECworld/WDS6_hands_on.git
```


Requirements

- All participants have received requirements for the registration to GEE API
 - https://github.com/PARSECworld/WDS6_hands_on/blob/main/requirements.pdf

Jupyter notebook code contains 3 parts [60min]

- **Part 1:** Explore the area of interest “Vale do Ribeira”
 - Source code [link](#)
 - Explore the census tract dataset
 - Explore the indicators dataset
 - Prepare the clusters data as a lat/long dataset

- **Part 2:** Download satellite images from GEE
 - Wait for downloading (it takes some time).
- **Part 3:** Process satellite images
 - Cropping imagery ready to training

Put here the
link to the code
from Ali

Contact us for future projects!

If you are interested in this topic, please feel free to contact us for collaboration.

Inter-University Research Institute Corporation
National Institutes for the Humanities
**Research Institute for
Humanity and Nature**

**TOKYO
METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY**

**THE UNIVERSITY
OF QUEENSLAND
AUSTRALIA**

Inter-University Research Institute Corporation
National Institutes for the Humanities
**Research Institute for
Humanity and Nature**

**TOKYO
METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY**

USP

**SO Southern OREGON
UNIVERSITY**

Thankyou

**AGU
100**

**ADVANCING EARTH
AND SPACE SCIENCE**

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

**BELMONT
FORUM**

The Nature
Conservancy

Powell Center

CESAB
CENTRE FOR THE SYNTHESIS AND ANALYSIS
OF BIODIVERSITY

AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA RECHERCHE
ANR

**THE UNIVERSITY
OF QUEENSLAND
AUSTRALIA**